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Challengers in energy transitions beyond renewable energy cooperatives: community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives in Spain

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Abstract

Over the last decade, grassroots challengers to the Spanish electricity regime have grown in number and diversity. But whilst ‘newer’ renewable actors have attracted increasing scholarly attention, ‘older’, affordability-oriented challengers remain under-studied, despite their evolution. Prompted by an interest in potential coalitions of challengers in Spain, we draw inspiration from the Multi-Level Perspective to explore how traditional, community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives ‘read’ the energy transition and act accordingly. Our analysis traces the evolution of one such cooperative, the Cooperativa Elèctrica d’Alginet (CEA), and draws on 16 interviews, secondary literature and media reports. We scrutinise how CEA frames changes in the landscape, windows of opportunity in the regime, and the evolution of challengers. Our key finding is a growing alignment of CEA with the frames espoused by the younger renewable cooperatives. This rapprochement invites further research about emerging political coalitions between extant and novel challengers in national electricity regimes.

Keywords: Energy transition; coalitions; multi-level perspective; challengers; Spain; electricity distribution cooperatives

Introduction

In 2018, the IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5 °C called for ‘rapid and far-reaching’ transitions in land, energy, industry, buildings, transport, and cities to keep climate change within a ‘safe’ range of warming in response to the global ecological crisis. In the energy domain, this is expected to translate into a future of clean, affordable, and safe energy sources. To make this prospect a reality, national and international authorities are setting binding targets for the penetration of renewables, set to be attained through national energy transitions. Thus, the European Union has set a target of 32% renewables by 2030; Germany has set itself the goal of an 80% renewable energy mix by 2050, whereas other countries have been more averse to ambitious targets (Aklin and Urpelainen 2018).

National energy transitions are diverse not only in how they intend to attain a low-carbon energy mix, but also in the composition, vigour, maturity, and radicality of the constellation of actors that challenge the norms, practices, imaginaries, etc. of the energy regime. Research in the European context has substantiated this diversity: from profit-seeking renewables businesses to decentralised individual renewable producers and community energy initiatives to radical grassroots organisations aspiring to materialise a deep democratisation of energy systems, the de-commodification of energy, the enshrinement of the right to energy, and the decentralisation of energy infrastructure (Bauwens, Gotchev, and Holstenkamp 2016; Becker, Kunze, and Vancea 2017; Fuchs and Hinderer 2016; Seyfang et al. 2014; Walker et al. 2010). Given this diversity, it is hardly surprising that niches of challengers have almost naturally formed coalitions and alliances. These coalitions are increasingly being recognised as a key feature behind the dynamics and trajectories of national energy transitions coalitions (Hess 2014). Be they discourse coalitions (Bosman et al. 2014; Munoz et al. 2014) or broader advocacy coalitions (Markard, Suter, and Ingold 2016; Szarka 2010), the literature is converging on the idea that the manner in which alliances between challengers are formed is highly relevant in reinforcing their position vis-à-vis the incumbents in energy regimes. Crucially for our discussion, the constitution of those political coalitions is connected with how actors make sense of national energy transitions (Hess 2018; Rosenbloom, Berton, and Meadowcroft 2016). If we seek to explore the potential of emerging coalitions against energy regimes, it is, therefore, vital to identify not only who are the relevant challengers and what they are doing, but also how they ‘read’ energy regimes and transitions and how they act accordingly.

But even though challengers and their coalitions are expanding, attention has often been focussed on just a few kind of stakeholders, particularly ‘newer’ and ‘greener’ challengers. This is the case of Spain, where one niche has so far gained a disproportionate amount of attention, at the expense of other more ‘conventional’ challengers. The newly-established renewable energy cooperatives such as Som Energia, Goiener, or EnergÉtica have attracted ever-increasing public, political and academic attention (Capellán-Pérez, Campos-Celador, and Terés-Zubiaga 2018; Heras-Saizarbitoria et al. 2018; Peller-Sifres et al. 2018; Riutort 2016). Founded from 2010 onward all over Spain by grassroots activists deeply distressed by the unsustainability and limited democracy of the electricity sector, they built their business model around retailing green-certified electricity to discontented and politicised customers. In the lapse of a few years they managed to attract tens of thousands of customers in an energy regime which, for decades, had seen only partial contestation to the dominance of a tiny number of incumbents – the five big companies that dominate the Spanish electricity market as an oligopoly (Rubio-Mondéjar and Garrués-Irurzun 2016). Their success must not be exaggerated, though. Large as it is, their customer base represents even today a minor share of Spain’s over 20 million customers. The five largest utilities continue to enjoy a position of overwhelming domination, with a total of 28.8 million delivery points (Sánchez-Ortiz et al. 2018). Also, and in contrast with the importance of local ownership of generating facilities in Denmark, Germany, and the United Kingdom, renewable electricity cooperatives in Spain have largely abstained from building community-owned solar plants and windmills and their model, equally inspired in the environmental movement and the social economy, is only partially embedded in the community.

Community embeddedness points to a key difference between young renewable electricity cooperatives and a niche of long-standing community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives. Community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives were born as early as the 1920s and 1930s, when dozens of electricity cooperatives spread all over Spain to provide affordable electricity to secondary, neglected localities. Some of these historical community-owned cooperatives arose in association with small hydropower facilities, which they owned (very similarly to the windmills owned by Danish farmers today); other community-owned electricity cooperatives simply raised local funds to connect a locality with the distant regional grid. After a series of ups and down in the decades from 1950 to 1980, the dozens of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives shrank to the 21 cooperatives which survive today in small localities in the regions of Valencia and Catalonia, and which, altogether with some municipality-owned utilities and other community-owned cooperatives sparsely scattered all over Spain, constitute a glaring exception to the virtual absence of community energy initiatives in the country (Romero-Rubio and de Andrés Díaz 2015; Vancea, Becker, and Kunze 2017). An additional singularity is that they are the only operators of local distribution grid besides the big five utilities, which distribute electricity to the vast majority of urban and rural localities in Spain under a model of regional monopoly. Though tiny in terms of the number of customers in comparison with the five big incumbents, the 21 community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives arguably remain by far the strongest niche of community energy initiatives in the Spanish electricity sector. Most interestingly, in the mid-2010s, some of them started to retail green-certified electricity to their local customers. A few of them also built their own solar generation plants as an experiment in renewable generation. Moreover, in late 2018 some community-owned and some renewable cooperatives joined forces to establish Unión Renovables, a lobby created to defend their common interests against the largest incumbent utilities. The foundation of this platform marked a historical turn in the trajectory of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives, which had for decades abstained from building bridges with other actors beyond their regional or local jurisdictions. It seems therefore that at some recent point in time the niche of historical cooperatives started to reflect on the need to adapt its practices to the increasing penetration and acceptance of renewables and the opportunities for new business models, thereby adding green concerns to their original core mission of providing affordable electricity to their communities. The fact that both groups of challengers decided to work together under the umbrella of a permanent organisation is probably testament to a fresh interpretation of the energy transition by the erstwhile affordability-focussed niche of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives.

However, regrettably enough, the niche of historical community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives, and their rapprochement with the younger renewable electricity cooperatives, has passed virtually unnoticed by academia. We know little or nothing about the grounds for the adoption of renewables and, more broadly, about how Spanish community-owned distribution cooperatives interpret the energy transition and how such frames shape their narratives and practices. It is very likely, though, that their views will differ from the more prominent niche of Spanish renewable electricity cooperatives. Given their rich history of decades of opposition to the incumbent regime, it is reasonable to anticipate that, once made aware of the contextual transformations brought about by the incipient energy transition in Spain, community-owned electricity distribution

cooperatives will have developed their own unique, practice-informed perspective about what the energy transition in Spain ought to achieve, as well as the preferable courses of action. Moreover, we know virtually nothing about the grounds for the rapprochement between renewable electricity cooperatives (largely motivated by the aim of greening and democratising the electricity regime), and community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives (originally driven by a core mission to supply affordable power to their local customers). The bias in favour of renewable energy cooperatives has obscured the analysis of this emerging coalition between new and 'old' challengers to the Spanish electricity regime, which could offer broader insights about the trajectories of national energy transitions. Our ignorance of the grounds for this rapprochement in the Spanish context speaks, therefore, to our broader analytical concern about the phenomenon of emerging political coalitions in national energy transitions, and inspires the leading objective of this research.

Bearing all of this in mind, the paper explores how the oft-neglected niche of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives 'read' the energy transition in Spain, what meanings they ascribe to it, and how they act accordingly. This standpoint calls for an exploration and understanding of potential and growing coalitions with the new generation of renewable cooperatives in Spain. To do so, we seek inspiration in the Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) (Geels 2002, 2011; Geels and Schot 2010) and, in particular, in inquiries about the frames that actors in niches of challengers adopt and mobilise to advance their cause in the extremely complex environment of socio-technical transitions. The use of MLP and framing theories narrows down our overall aims to two questions: how are the historical community-owned distribution electricity cooperatives in Spain framing the energy transition? And, how close or far are their framings from those appertaining to the niche of renewable electricity cooperatives? Our findings in response to these questions allow us to take up our overarching concern with the political coalitions between challengers. We thereby elaborate some final reflections on the extent to which the proximity and distance in the framings of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives and renewable electricity cooperatives may provide grounds for potential alliances.

To address these questions, we narrow down our focus to a particularly rich case study, that is, one of the most dynamic community-owned distribution cooperatives, the Cooperativa Elèctrica d'Alginet (CEA), in the Valencia region. CEA distributes and retails electricity to approximately 6,000 local customers as well as to a limited number of regional public bodies, and was established in the late 1920s in the wake of the explosion in community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives mentioned above. Throughout decades, the main purpose of CEA was delivering affordable electricity to the households, commerce, and industries in Alginet. But after decades of little organisational change, over the last decade or so CEA started to grow quite considerably in terms of turnover and staff, and expanded from conventional business segments to embrace energy generation and telecommunications. CEA's social outreach activities also expanded. Last but not least, in 2015 CEA started to retail green-certified renewable electricity to its local customer base. Also, CEA was one of the founding members of Unión Renovables, the joint lobby mentioned above. As CEA retained the key traits shared by all Spanish community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives whilst it also started to adopt additional 'greener' practices, the case of CEA can offer key insights into the dynamics,

and especially the framings, underlying the rapprochement between community-owned distribution cooperatives and renewable energy cooperatives.

The paper is organised as follows. Following this Introduction, the next section discusses the insights that the MLP—connected with framing approaches in social movements theories—can offer to scrutinise how niches of challengers respond to the present ecological crisis by mobilising the frames that they consider most convenient to their cause. Subsequently, we present our methods. From then on, and with the help of our framework, we explore how CEA—our illustrative case study of the niche community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives in Spain—frames the energy transition. Hence, we examine how CEA interprets the pressures of the landscape, i.e. the global ecological crisis; explore the ways in which CEA interprets the ongoing transformations in the electricity and the opportunities available to change it; and finally, scrutinise how CEA self-identifies itself as a challenger and its attitudes toward the challenges posed by other niches. In the same section, and for the sake of a contrast, we also put the framings of CEA into dialogue with those of the better-known niche of renewable energy cooperatives. We conclude by discussing the grounds for potential alliances between niches of challengers, and also suggest some avenues for further research.

The multi-level perspective: landscape, regime and niches

Socio-technical transitions literature offers a framework that focuses on the transformation of the key features of different systems of production and consumption such as food, transport, housing, finance, or energy. It has been widely used to address and understand process of change within these systems (Smith 2007). Essentially, this literature is concerned with the characteristics and dimensions of systems and how the dynamics and processes change over time. The MLP framework has sought, within this literature, to organise the analysis of socio-technical change by considering that a socio-technical system consists of niches, regimes, and landscapes (Geels 2010), and attempted to offer a more complex and systemic approach to socio-technical change dynamics.

From MLP, socio-technical configurations in regimes are stable and dominant ways of realising a particular societal function; that is, they are dominant configurations of practices, relations, discourses, etc. (Smith, Voß, and Grin 2010). According to Geels (2002), there are several dimensions that characterise a given regime: its guiding principles (i.e. the overall ideas and assumptions driving the system); the technologies used; the industrial structure (i.e. the relationships between stakeholders in production processes); user relations and channels to access goods and services (i.e. infrastructure, modalities, and interactions for accessing); the policies and regulations (i.e. normative and legal aspects governing production, distribution, and consumption); the forms and sources of knowledge used, produced and legitimised by the system; and the culture (i.e. social and cultural patterns).

However, a number of niches exist in a system. These are spaces in which alternative, less visible practices take place. They are protective spaces where different ideas, models, configurations, and ways of doing try to survive and develop. Niches present configurations whose characteristics are different to those of the dominant regime: they may work with different guiding principles; may use different technologies; present

different relations between stakeholders, channels and user practices; or may privilege different sources of knowledge and alternative cultures. Regimes are usually stable, whereas niches usually evolve quickly as they are spaces of permanent experimentation and change (Geels 2002). Niches are the place of transformative ideas and practices, but their potential is constrained or enabled by the more powerful structures of the regime (Bos and Grin 2008; Geels 2014). Practices in niches may have very different attitudes regarding regimes (Geels and Schot 2007), so different kinds of niche-regime interactions may take place. This may depend on the landscape and its pressures, on the stability of the regime, on the maturity of niches, but also on the views and strategies of niches. In this diversity of attitudes, niches may just try to shield and to protect themselves in a given regime; to empower themselves; and/or to scale by adapting to the regime or by conflicting, trying to eventually substitute it. Strategies vary from more adaptive and reformist to more contentious.

In the theory of socio-technical change of MLP (Geels 2002, 2010, 2011), regimes try to survive and remain stable, but they are permanently exposed to pressures derived from external, powerful and long-term economic, social, cultural or environmental trends (Rotmans, Kemp, and van Asselt 2001), which constitute the landscape. Transition in systems may take place when the regime is destabilised because of the heavy pressure of the landscape, so windows of opportunity may open up for niches—if they are mature enough—to influence or even completely replace the regime (Geels 2002). As Smith, Voß, and Grin (2010, 441–42) see it, this framework ‘links specific innovation activities configured in niches with structural transformations in regimes’.

The MLP has generated helpful insights about the evolution, the trajectories and, more generally, the dynamics and regularities that govern low-carbon transitions (Geels et al. 2017; Scoones, Leach, and Newell 2015; Verbong and Geels 2010). Interestingly for our purposes, in the context of low-carbon transition in the United Kingdom, the MLP has been employed to explore the transformative potential of niches of challengers driven by community values, not by environmentalism, much less the ambition to bring about an energy transition (Seyfang et al. 2014; Seyfang, Park, and Smith 2013). Others have looked at a similar phenomenon in other contexts (Becker, Kunze, and Vancea 2017; Islar and Busch 2016).

In this paper, we take our cue from this stream of research by concentrating on those niches beyond grassroots environmentalism. However, we depart from a different standpoint: this stream of research based on MLP has been used to describe the trajectories and dynamics of change of specific niches in energy transition processes. By contrast, we are interested in addressing the visions of specific niches regarding the transitions processes, the motivations, judgements and perspectives of these processes of change they are engaged in. In other words, how they understand dynamics between landscape, energy regime, and the different niches. This position echoes the ideas of some authors who invite us to interrogate regime-niche dynamics by drawing on the visions of the actors and their interactions with the visions and activities of others, instead of just relying upon predetermined classifications (Köhren 2018).

To address this question, some new ideas have to be connected with MLP concepts. To this end, we follow the work of Smith et al. (2016) regarding the potential connection between socio-technical transitions and social movement theories. The authors highlight that the idea of framing in social movement literature has proved to be very relevant in

order to understand how movements are held together by a collective production of ideas and meaning, how they strategise and how they develop their activities collectively. This notion can be used in the analysis of innovation movements in the pursue of more sustainable systems (2016). In fact, the idea has been used to better understand innovation activities in general in various domains (e.g. Hess 2016; Scoones, Leach, and Newell 2015).

The notion of framing, as developed by social-constructivist social movement scholars, refers to the process of meaning production in the environment that enables a movement to build a narrative (Snow et al. 1986), and to think about which actions are to be undertaken to address a problem and achieve change (Tarrow 1998). Frames are schemes of interpretation that ‘help to render events or occurrences meaningful and thereby function to organize experience and guide action [...] action-oriented sets of beliefs and meanings that inspire and legitimate the activities’ of a given organisation (Benford and Snow 2000, 614). It is a very relevant idea to understand the dynamics of mobilisation of potential adherents and constituents, or of demobilisation of antagonists (Snow and Benford 1988). Interestingly, framing theory has already inspired penetrating analyses of national energy transitions (Haas 2018, 2019; Hess 2019).

From this standpoint, we now refine our initial questions in light of the above discussion, asking ourselves: how does a given stakeholder consider the regime and its role in transforming it? How does it consider the opportunities and limits opened in a system by the pressures of the landscape? And how does it consider other stakeholders and the practices of other challengers in the niche (for example, whether they are allies or competitors) in order to overcome the regime?

For the specific aims of our study, these questions may help to reveal how challengers beyond the more militant and contentious grassroots energy environmentalists promote alternative practices, and how they relate, or may relate, with distinct niches of challengers. They may not be directly denouncing the model or the powerful actors, nor fully reframing the idea of energy transition. They may be newcomers or old and well-established stake- holders; all the same, they aspire to change the electricity regime in response to transformations in energy landscape. In any case, they are also developing practices beyond the mainstream. As we will see, in the Spanish low-carbon transition, challengers have emerged in the form of renewable profit-seeking businesses, decentralised on-grid producers, renewable electricity cooperatives and—somewhat unexpectedly—community energy initiatives.

Methods

Our analysis is based on the purposeful selection of one case from among the population of twenty-one community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives in Spain. Although it is not representative of the whole population, our purposive choice is helpful to illustrate some of the population’s features. The main reason is that our case study has retained over its transformation the basic characteristics of all community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives in Spain, whilst, at the same time, adding a set of green practices that appear to respond to a growing concern with the demands and opportunities brought about by the present ecological crisis. Two exploratory interviews (with four representatives of other community-owned cooperatives and with a member of staff of

the regional umbrella organisation of electricity distribution cooperatives) confirmed the similarities as well as the frontrunner status of CEA in at least two domains: innovation projects and community outreach. The advantages of CEA are therefore a balanced combination of business and social orientation, as well as the existence of a clear-cut organisational renaissance in the early 2000s which coincided with the initial steps of the energy transition in Spain. We discarded another frontrunner in the adoption of green practices, Enercoop. Enercoop and CEA are by far the largest cooperatives in terms of number of customers (approx. 14,000 and 6,000 affiliates, respectively), as well as the only ones which have customers beyond their original local demarcation and have participated in innovation projects in the European Union. Enercoop was founded in 1925 in Crevillent (population 29,000) to contribute to the technological renovation of a thriving textile industry in the area. More recently, Enercoop not only consolidated its activities, but also embarked upon a path of considerable growth, to the extent of making some inroads into the German and Portuguese generation and retail markets in the early 2010s. This path led Enercoop to partially blur its community embeddedness as the focus of its business model broadened. For this reason, we opted for CEA over Enercoop. Apart from CEA and Enercoop, the remaining electricity distribution cooperatives are smaller in size, with the more modest of them supplying only a few dozen customers.

The deliberate selection of one case study is acceptable in view of the objective of exploring an information-rich case and the absence of any claim to representativeness of the wider population of distribution cooperatives (Yin 1994). Time, logistical and, especially, budgetary constraints also influenced our decision. This choice has obvious limitations for our ultimate goal of exploring the potential ground for a coalition between the niche of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives and renewable electricity cooperatives, the most patent being that our findings cannot speak for the whole niche of which CEA is a member. We address this constraint by asking our informants in CEA not only about their organisation, but also about the niche as a whole (of which they are a privileged observer). Although this may introduce some degree of bias, we think that it may help to address the limitations of the choice of a single case study. Also, and as far as the framings by the renewable electricity cooperatives are concerned, we build upon the fact that these actors have been subject to greater attention by the literature and that, accordingly, their framings can be accessed through existing research. As far as CEA is concerned, our study draws primarily on individual and group interviews with a total of 16 informants. We interviewed eight informants from CEA: three members of the board, including the sitting President; three members of the executive team, namely the Managing Director, the Technical Director and the manager of innovation projects; and two additional members of staff, namely one from the commercial department, and one member of the intervention and repairs team. One goal of these objectives was to identify milestones in CEA's business and social outreach strategies. Accordingly, we opted to carry out this exercise with those informants who have worked for CEA the longest. This allows us to make a contrast between the present and the previous trajectory of CEA, before the 2000s. We jointly constructed a timeline of events starting in the early 2000s, covering two dimensions: breakthroughs in the business model and in social outreach practices. Additionally, we conducted four individual interviews with external informants cognisant of the activities of CEA. These informants worked for the local council, a supra-municipal energy agency set up by the local councils in the area, as well as for the largest agricultural cooperative in Alginet. The fourth informant was a member of staff of the

umbrella organisation representing the interests of the electricity distribution cooperatives in the Valencia region. The aim of these four interviews was twofold: to contrast the information provided by informants from CEA, as well as to gather data about the context in which CEA operates. Lastly, we also held a group interview with a panel of four representatives of small and medium-sized electricity distribution cooperatives (all smaller than CEA). Overall, we interviewed eleven male and five female informants. All interviews were carried out between December 2017 and April 2018.

Our choice of informants, particularly within CEA, was based on two criteria: diversity of positions within the cooperative and data saturation. Out of a total universe of approximately 30 members of staff, we set ourselves the goal of interviewing between 6 and 12 informants. Informants were identified with the help of two members of staff from CEA, who acted both as our gatekeepers and central nodes in our exercise of reference sampling. As a consequence, the voices of members of staff and board members of CEA may be slightly over-represented in our non-representative sample, and voices critical of the recent strategy of the cooperative may be under-represented or even silenced. Given the scope of the research, it was not feasible to expand the scope of informants. However, the interviews, our own observation, as well as the interviews held with informants external to CEA, do not suggest to us the existence of a distinct body of opinion contrary to or substantially divergent from the views and facts presented to us by the CEA staff interviewed.

Framing the spanish energy transition beyond the niche of renewable electricity cooperatives: the case of Cooperativa Elèctrica d'Alginet

The Cooperativa Elèctrica d'Alginet distributes and retails electricity to approximately 6,000 local customers as well as to a limited number of regional public bodies. The origins of CEA can be traced back to 1929, when a few local notables and entrepreneurs mustered the capital required to connect Alginet (population 13,000) to a nearby electric line. Alginet achieved this, as did a further 15 localities in the Valencia region (Eléctrica Meliana 1998; Federación de Cooperativas Eléctricas de la Comunidad Valenciana 1992; Giménez Guarinos et al. 2011). In these localities, economic activity was dominated by agriculture. Being short of industries, Alginet was therefore uninviting for the private utilities that, in the early twentieth century, slowly extended their grids across the Valencia region. Even today, agriculture accounts for 25% of all economic production in Alginet. Despite this, and after decades of little organisational change, CEA has managed to grow quite considerably in terms of turnover and staff over the last decade, to the point that it has seen an increase in the workforce from seven to thirty in this period. This growth has gone hand in hand with an expansion from conventional business segments to embrace energy generation and telecommunications in Alginet. Indeed, CEA's business and social outreach activities have boomed over the last fifteen years. Throughout this period, the main purpose of CEA continued to be the delivery of low-priced electricity to the households, commerce, and industries in Alginet. This is in line with the founding aim of contributing to the welfare and economic development of the locality. Nevertheless, the original purpose simultaneously expanded in new directions, especially toward the provision of social benefits to the community, the diffusion of environmental values, and the supply of renewable electricity. CEA also made genuine attempts to increase the participation of its affiliates.

For CEA and the rest of the electricity distribution cooperatives, the liberalisation of the Spanish electric sector in 1997 opened up fresh opportunities. Between 2004 and 2013, a renewable boom spurred the consolidation of a plethora of new challengers to the long-time hegemony of the five largest electric utilities (Endesa, Iberdrola, Gas Natural Fenosa, Energías de Portugal Hidrocarbónico, and Viesgo). Solar farms ranging from a just a few to dozens of megawatts blossomed across rural areas of Spain. They provided a conduit for the investments of middle-class investors and international funds. Renewable businesses developed thousands of megawatts of wind parks alongside the renewable branches of the big five utilities. Overall, large-scale wind parks and the solar industry thrived from 2004 onwards. Indeed, by 2008 Spain had become the largest solar market worldwide, and a world leader in concentrated solar power technologies. Spain leapt from 45 photovoltaic installations registered before 2000 to more than 51,000 in 2008.

In the same period, domestic production of photovoltaic products grew from €72 to €645 million, and imports from €34 million to €5.4 billion (del Río and Mir-Artigues 2014). The 400 MW target set by the government for 2005 was exceeded by a factor of almost ten (Gómez, Dopazo, and Fueyo 2016). Still, by the late 2000s the Spanish electric mix was still largely fossil (AEVAL 2011). Moreover, the early 2010s witness a policy U-turn which public authorities and big incumbents presented as a response to the ‘tariff deficit’ (Ciarreta, Espinosa, and Pizarro-Irizar 2014; CNMC 2016; OECD and IEA 2015; Stenzel and Frenzel 2008), and which ultimately brought to a halt new investments in renewables and, especially, in solar (Haas 2018). As a result, by late 2014, for instance, the political economy of the electricity sector in Spain had barely altered. The five largest electric utilities continued to enjoy a position of overwhelming domination, as they supplied electricity to a total of 28.8 million delivery points (Sánchez-Ortiz et al. 2018). Also, by the end of the renewable boom, the ecosystem of challengers in Spain showed little or no presence of local, community-owned renewable facilities. This set Spain in contrast with the importance of local ownership of generating facilities in Denmark, Germany and the United Kingdom, or with the strength of community-owned electricity cooperatives in France and Italy. In Spain, by contrast, renewable electricity cooperatives largely abstained from building community-owned solar plants and windmills, or even community-embedded retail cooperatives.

Against this backdrop of major changes in the power sector in Spain, the new Board of CEA, elected in 2004, brought about an injection of fresh ideas. The new Board members were motivated by the aspiration to attain higher levels of affiliates’ participation and to expand the activities of the cooperative beyond the mere supply of low-priced electricity. The new Board focussed upon two lines of action: on the one hand, to improve the quality of electric supply and, more broadly, of the services offered by the cooperative to its customers; and on the other hand, to strengthen the programme of subsidies and grants to a range of social groups in Alginet, especially those most seriously affected by the economic crisis that erupted in 2008. Thereby, the first breakthrough came from the aspiration to find a lasting solution to the recurrent restrictions in the supply of power established by Iberdrola, the second largest private utility in Spain according to the number of contracts (2017). Iberdrola also owns, and operates as a monopoly, the regional distribution grid from which CEA obtained the electricity. Recurrent restrictions on the amount of power delivered by Iberdrola resulted in blackouts and restrictions in load-shedding exercises for CEA’s customers. As a result, by 2007 CEA had filed 25 lawsuits against Iberdrola.

The new Board set the ground for a series of breakthroughs in the business model. The first, started in the mid-2000s, was the construction of an electric substation. The substation, finalised in 2012, allowed CEA to bypass Iberdrola and connect Alginet to the semi-public national grid. This move not only improved the quality of supply to customers in Alginet, it also earned CEA almost complete independence from a fierce competitor. A second breakthrough in the business model occurred in 2008 thanks to the complete rollout of smart metres across the entire CEA grid. The rollout was completed ten years ahead of the deadline set by the authorities for the whole of Spain. Once deployed, smart metres revolutionised the billing process. Costs dropped, and several sources of human error were eradicated: human readings, estimated bills, and discrepancies between customers and CEA concerning impromptu lofty bills. Also, the information about consumption supplied by the smart metres allowed CEA to offer better advisory services, especially as far as energy efficiency is concerned. This became particularly important once instances of fuel poverty increased considerably after 2008. Suddenly, the early and successful deployment of smart metres put CEA on the radar of a number of technological partners interested in implementing pilot projects on the management of smart grids. In particular, the Spanish technological transnational ETRA invited CEA, in the early 2010s, to participate in two Europe-wide projects: Nobel Grid and Hyrim. Besides helping CEA to acquire cutting-edge technical know-how, both projects also raised its visibility vis-à-vis key Spanish and European actors in the power sector, including policy-makers, and facilitated new technological alliances. At the same time, these projects also boosted CEA's visibility and prestige in Alginet, given the notoriety achieved in the local media. Accordingly, a third breakthrough resulted from its participation, since 2011, in various technological innovation projects (Nobel Grid and Hyrim). In these projects, CEA provided a test bed for the management of smart grids. The last of these projects, Nobel Grid, yielded the design of an open-code smart metre intended to support distributed renewable generation, energy efficiency, electric vehicle recharge, and other measures intended to fight climate change. Last but not least, 2015 brought the shift to retailing electricity certified from renewable sources.

As far as social outreach is concerned, the new Board soon increased the range and amount of grants and subsidies to social groups in Alginet. Such allowances had traditionally focussed on social and sports clubs. Soon, other organisations started to receive financial assistance from CEA, including music clubs, a local festivity group, the Easter brotherhoods, and also local writers who experienced difficulties in seeing their works published. In 2005, CEA started to subsidise the 'day of the electric cooperative' more generously on the occasion of the local festivities; in 2008, a discount for retirees was set up; in 2011, CEA inaugurated a programme that subsidises primary and secondary school textbooks as well as the expenses involved in end-of-course trips; in 2013, it instituted a food subsidy for the neediest; and in 2016, it started to sponsor a 'cooperative village' in India. All these subsidies were met with warm approval by the affiliates and the population of Alginet. Affiliates began to show an earnest interest in the calendar and modalities of delivering the subsidies, as reflected in a higher turnout in the annual assemblies in which such proposals are approved. These programmes were set up with the goal of ensuring that no one in the community was left behind, particularly given the scale and depth of the economic crisis. The allowances were designed to ensure that beneficiaries would spend the amount involved in the largest possible number of local shops, thus boosting the local economy.

All of the former invites us to explore the credentials of CEA as part and parcel of a niche of challengers to the Spanish electricity regime. Accordingly, in the three sub-sections that follow, we undertake this exploration with the analytical assistance of the Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) and framing theories. We pay particular attention to the three central concepts of landscape, regime, and niche. Thus, according to our first two research questions (re framings and their proximity between niches of challengers), we examine how CEA interprets the pressures of the landscape, i.e. the global ecological crisis; we explore in what ways CEA reads the evolution of the electricity regime as a result, inter alia, of the energy transition; and, finally, we scrutinise how CEA self-identifies itself as a challenger and its attitudes toward the challenges posed by other niches.

Interpreting the landscape: how CEA reads the pressures of the environmental crisis

CEA reading of the pressure of the environmental crisis (as a landscape phenomenon, in the MLP language) over the present society rests on an overwhelming consensus, as manifested by both the staff and board members interviewed. This consensus implies that the central challenge for contemporary societies is the over-consumption of resources and, ultimately, their depletion. Accordingly, the response must build on a wide-ranging strategy of education and environmental awareness in two directions: more efficient uses of energy and the attenuation of the negative impacts of electricity generation by means of a long-term, complete shift to renewables.

Indeed, this is what CEA has sought to achieve over the last decade and a half, by promoting environmental awareness on energy efficiency and the benefits of renewable energies. In the early 2010s CEA launched a campaign against 'energy vampires' to incentivise the substitution of inefficient domestic appliances, stand-by consumption, and other sources of waste. CEA also encouraged and delivered demonstrative workshops in schools and social gatherings. By contrast, as far as renewables are concerned, the recent trajectory of CEA has only incorporated this aspect very recently through a project launched in late 2017 to build a photovoltaic facility in the grounds of the substation. Indeed, this project was conceived more as a project of environmental awareness than in terms of its contribution to the cooperative's generation mix. Despite the self-proclaimed commitment to renewable production amongst CEA staff and the Board, more photovoltaic projects failed to materialise due to their insufficient financial returns. Thus, the growth of environmental awareness within CEA is due to its growing exposition to the initiatives of Spanish and European renewable energy cooperatives (accessed through Europe-wide innovation projects, sectoral fora or new platforms such as Unión Renovables). Overall, however, actions in favour of environmental sustainability have only partially permeated the core business of CEA, even if sales of renewable electricity are considered. At any rate, the growing environmental awareness has remained secondary to the original purpose of delivering access to affordable electricity for the community. The actions toward increasing environmental awareness in the local community aim to improve environmental attitudes and uses of energy, and only to a lesser extent to provide business services to customers that allow them to shift to more transformative patterns of electricity consumption.

Interpreting the regime: how CEA reads the evolution of the Spanish electricity system

CEA's major concern with the Spanish electricity regime is its unfairness vis-à-vis electricity distribution cooperatives. This is CEA's major concern, above the lack of sustainability of the electricity sector. The unfair treatment of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives vis-à-vis profit-oriented private utilities stems from the imposition of the same requirements to organisations of a very diverse nature. Thus, Spanish regulations request the same financial requisites and volumes of information from the small electricity distribution cooperatives as from the big five distribution utilities. For example, CEA staff repeatedly mention that, before 2007, the regulatory framework required electric cooperatives to register in the Commercial Register, which according to Spanish law can only register private companies. For CEA this de facto asymmetry not only overlooks the sheer difference in the size of the customer base (thousands versus millions). It also disavows the crucial fact that, until 1997, the big five distribution utilities operated as state-sanctioned regional monopolies. The privileged market status of the dominant incumbents today is a carryover of their privileged position in the past (Garrués-Irurzun 2010). Closely connected to the accusation of unfairness is the idea that the legal architecture of the Spanish electricity system leads to unequal access to policymakers and, ultimately, to the capture of the regulators by the big utilities. A common complaint amongst the top staff of CEA is that they are unable to find a way to enter into direct dialogue with the highest echelons of policymakers in the central government. Finally, a growing concern of CEA is the issue of fuel poverty. As the issue grew in relevance after 2008 and CEA responded with specific measures, its staff also became more sensitised to the problem. An implication of this growing awareness is that fuel poverty has been identified as a systemic problem of the electricity regime in Spain, and, therefore, an area that calls for specific actions to be taken by CEA in the near future.

Despite its harsh criticism of the unfairness of the Spanish electricity regime, CEA does not disavow the major transformations happening in association with the energy transition. The CEA staff are totally convinced of the inevitability of a 100% renewable electricity mix in the near future. Moreover, they also see a major opportunity in the ongoing spatial reconfiguration of the electricity regime in favour of decentralised technologies. A common representation of the not-so-distant future presents a national grid co-existing with decentralised smart grids, electric vehicles and smart electric appliances in house-holds. In this future regime scenario, CEA envisions considerable opportunities for local, community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives, given that they own and operate the local distribution grid. This new scenario is expected to take decades to materialise, however. Furthermore, in this new scenario, the core mission of CEA is expected to continue to be the provision of affordable electricity to its local community.

'Seeing' other niches: how CEA interprets the relation with other challengers

CEA staff sympathise with the efforts of challengers in favour of a greener and more democratic electricity regime. Above all, they have a positive attitude towards those actors which abide by the principles of the social economy, i.e. the renewable electricity cooperatives. A general observation is that, faced with the magnitude of the sustainability crisis, all efforts are viewed as beneficial by the CEA staff.

At the same time, the CEA staff also acknowledge the relevant differences with renewable energy cooperatives. First, whilst the latter are moved by the explicit aspiration to transform the energy regime in a renewable and democratic direction, the core mandate of CEA is seen as the provision of cheap, affordable electricity to its customer base in Alginet. Cheap electricity is conceived as the major benefit that CEA provides to the community, above even the social outreach activities already mentioned. Secondly, CEA perceive another major discrepancy in the models of electricity distribution cooperatives and the new wave of renewable electricity cooperatives. Although both operate according to the principles of the social economy, CEA see their model as facilitating the participation of the member base to a higher degree. The physical proximity between affiliates and staff, as well as the embeddedness of the latter in the local community of Alginet (most of them were born and live in Alginet), render participation both more effective and more profound. By contrast, the national scope of the largest renewable energy cooperatives and the spread of their local groups of activists is regarded as a serious obstacle to effective participation. Thirdly, CEA perceive its strategies of regime change to differ from the strategy pursued by renewable electricity cooperatives. Whereas CEA's strategy is seen as incremental and interstitial—much in line with the approach to social change of the cooperative movement (Sempere and Garcia 2014)—the overarching strategy of the renewable electricity cooperatives is portrayed as disruptive and too abrupt, in addition to being, perhaps, counter-productive, given the need to muster broad support for energy transition from the general public.

The strategy of regime change thus builds more upon the representation of interests and less upon social mobilisation. To that end, the umbrella platform of electricity distribution cooperatives in the Valencia region remains the crucial tool. The Federación de Cooperativas Eléctricas de la Comunitat Valenciana was founded in 1984 after a period of intense litigation with the regional distribution monopoly, Hidroeléctrica Española (now Iberdrola). The Federación was especially helpful in the conflict with this incumbent, as it helped to secure the support of the regional government and ultimately broker a lasting settlement. Later on, the Federation also took an active role in advocating a specific regulation for cooperative utilities within the Spanish regulatory framework, something yet to be secured. All in all, this implies that Unión Renovables can be helpful, but for CEA the foremost tool for lobbying remains its federation with other cooperatives.

Proximate framings as a ground for potential coalitions

We conclude our presentation and discussion of our findings by briefly putting the framings of CEA into dialogue with those of better known renewable electricity cooperatives. The previous section already discussed the proximity between CEA and the niche of challengers of renewable electricity cooperatives. Thus, in what follows, we concentrate on three elements which touch upon the regime and the landscape and in which the proximities and distances between CEA and the renewable electricity cooperatives may have a bearing on the ground for a future coalition between both niches.

The first element is the identification of the most pressing environmental issue which will determine the future of the power sector. CEA staff largely interpret the environmental pressures from the landscape as an issue of over-consumption and resource depletion which, in the energy sector, is palpable in the exhaustion of fossil fuels. Renewable energy

cooperatives, however, tend to adopt a broader view and point to the multiple aspects of an ecological crisis of which resource depletion and climate change are but manifestations, however important. This discrepancy finds a correlate in the representations by each side of how actors and policymakers must respond to the environmental crisis. The CEA places more emphasis on the transition toward a 100% renewable energy mix, and understands efforts in energy efficiency and the reduction of energy consumption as necessary, mostly as long as fossil fuels are still used. While, for renewable electricity cooperatives, a future of energy scarcity is often the inescapable scenario, either as a result of the drastic efforts required to keep global warming below 1.5 °C or of a lesser availability of energy sources. What is important to bear in mind here, however, is that in spite of the diverging visions about the required 'fix' to the environmental crisis there is considerable agreement on the actions that must be taken, and which include more renewable generation, the electrification of the supply of energy, the decentralisation of the architecture of the electricity system and the deployment of smart grids and the empowerment of the customer.

The second element concerns the aspirational future of the energy sector, which both CEA and renewable electricity cooperatives place under the label of 'energy democracy'. Again, some degree of discrepancy is present about how each party conceptualises this idea. Both attach the utmost relevance to the empowerment of citizens in their role as users of energy. This is intimately connected with aspects that lie at the core of the frames of CEA and the renewable energy cooperatives (and also advocacy platforms such as Plataforma por un Nuevo Modelo Energético) and that conceive energy democracy as implying the de-commodification of energy (energy conceptualised as a commons), more participation of citizens in the energy system and the decentralisation of the power system via off-grid and smart grid architectures. This latter element points to a first difference about the future. Whereas CEA tends to downplay the role of decentralised technologies in the desired image of the power system, renewable electricity cooperatives make a stronger case for the benefits and necessity of such technologies. Also, as mentioned above, CEA attaches greater salience to the participation of customers from local communities in electricity cooperatives in their localities, an ideal of empowerment which they see hard to attain under the organisation model of renewable electricity cooperatives whose mass of affiliates spreads all over Spain. Although hardly insurmountable, the differences regarding decentralisation and the possibility of citizen empowerment find a reflection in discrepancies about the priorities that must guide the national policies of the energy transition and the weight of the local in the hypothesis of change that must be embraced by those grassroots challengers that may wish to see energy democracy materialise some day.

Lastly, a third aspect which impinges upon the proximities and distances in the frames of CEA and the renewable electricity cooperatives concerns the importance of fuel poverty in the strategies of each party. It was mentioned above that, as the crisis initiated in 2008 escalated and local communities started to suffer the consequences, CEA and other community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives became more concerned with the negative consequences for their communities and launched specific actions to address the difficulties of their affiliates and customers. The niche of renewable electricity cooperatives also focussed on this issue and mobilised a narrative that portrayed energy poverty as a violation of the right to energy and a direct consequence of the commodification of energy by the electricity market. However, renewable electricity

cooperatives incorporated the issue in their core business activities to a lesser degree. The probable reason is that their customer base included a larger share of the middle class, who were less affected by energy poverty. At any rate, renewable electricity cooperatives mobilised against energy poverty by supporting the actions of advocacy platforms such as Plataforma por un Nuevo Modelo Energético or Aliança contra la Pobresa Energètica, and less by means of specific measures incorporated to their core activity. Again, this marks a difference in emphasis between CEA and renewable electricity cooperatives about the actions required to attain the desired energy transition. Overall, in this section we have illustrated three key discrepancies in the framings of CEA and the niche of renewable electricity cooperatives. Nevertheless, this ought not to obscure the extensive and fundamental agreement about the urgency of addressing the ecological crisis, the desirability of materialising the principle of energy democracy, and, above all, the necessity of an energy transition from the grassroots.

Conclusion

In this paper we set out to explore the framings mobilised by the niche of community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives in Spain as a means of unpacking their understandings about the energy transition. To this end, we have demonstrated the growing alignment of one electricity distribution cooperative in Spain, CEA, with the aims of the energy transition. Our main contribution has been to characterise the orientation of CEA toward the energy transition, as evidenced in the views about the energy transition they manifest. In particular, we have explored attitudes within CEA toward the transformations in the landscape, the opportunities opened up by ongoing changes in the regime and the attendant niche of renewable electricity cooperatives.

How community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives 'read' the energy transition is relevant for the future trajectory of the energy transition in Spain two reasons. First, this segment of actors has shown that it can provide the platform to nurture major technical and managerial innovations which may, eventually, be subject to adoption or even scaling up by other actors or the electricity regime as a whole. The innovations introduced by CEA in smart metering and smart grid management, as well as the attendant embryonic practices in energy efficiency are good illustrations. Second, the positive attitude of CEA toward renewable electricity cooperatives, demonstrated by the creation of a common platform for advocacy and public awareness-raising, and the increase in environmental awareness within CEA owing to a growing exposition to the discourses and practices of Spanish and European renewable energy cooperatives, intimate the possibility of further alliances between segments of challengers. As pro-transition policies in Spain are likely to expand and intensify in the near future, we can reasonably anticipate additional opportunities for alignment between the segment of electricity distribution cooperatives and niches of grassroots challengers. A major policy implication of this alignment concerns the deployment of self-consumption, renewable and local energy communities. The European Union has placed these three drivers at the centre of an energy transition that empowers European citizens and involves them in the fight against climate change and the present ecological crisis. Also, the Ministry of Ecological Transition has repeatedly signalled that renewable and local energy communities will be a pivotal driver of the energy transition in Spain. The embeddedness of 'greener' community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives provides an excellent platform for the creation of renewable

energy communities at the local level. The latter can benefit from shared understandings about the need to develop models of supply based on the principles of the social economy, whilst at the same time build upon a complementary cross-fertilization between affordability-oriented distribution cooperatives and the more environmentally-aware renewable energy cooperatives. Arguably, community-owned electricity distribution cooperatives can offer a site for experimentation toward local and renewable energy communities, whilst regional or country-wide renewable electricity cooperatives are in an ideal position to scale up the ideals and practices of local energy communities.

Conceptually, the above also invites a further exploration of the nature, aims, trajectories, and strategies of coalitions of challengers in the Spanish energy transition between organisations moved by environmental concerns and those motivated by affordability, community welfare, and other purposes. As a complement to the slightly more widely researched political coalitions between emergent and 'new' challengers, mostly motivated by environmental concerns (Hess 2014; Hess 2018), we suggest exploring the 'unconventional' coalitions of 'new' and 'old' challengers in a complementary sense, based on the partial overlap of discursive frames. To do so, one suggested avenue would be to follow the work of Smith et al. (2016) regarding the potential connection between socio-technical transitions and social movement theories. As Smith et al. indicate, the idea of framing in social movement literature has proven very helpful to understand how social movements are held together by the collective production of ideas and meaning and their contribution to creating a sense of solidarity and informing action. This parallel between political coalitions in national energy transitions and social movement may be somehow obscured in the formulation of pathways for socio-technical transitions (Geels et al. 2016; Geels and Schot 2007), despite some theoretical elaboration (Geels 2010). Therefore, we suggest to scrutinise how the encounter between the framings of conventional and disruptive challengers may yield the prospect of new discursive elaborations and, eventually, of yet unborn pathways for national energy transitions.

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